

Towards Digital Twins of buildings and smart energy networks: Current and future trends

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Abstract— The European Union is actively promoting the digitalization of energy systems as a mean of achieving urban decarbonization. In addition, the future expansion of distributed energy networks, prosumers (for both heating and electricity) and electric vehicles, will create the need for a smart real-time and predictive management. In this framework, Digital Twins will play a key role offering management tools and planning strategies in urban energy systems. Given the recent emergence of this technology, this work aims to elucidate the definition of Digital Twin by conducting a comprehensive review of various practical applications and methodologies outlined in the current literature. This analysis will examine different applications in the context of buildings, district heating networks, and micro-grids, exploring different scopes, such as fault detection, energy saving and support for grid operators. Additionally, several methodologies for developing Digital Twins will be highlighted including Deep Learning and physical-based algorithms. Finally, the benefits of smart networks and buildings using Digital Twins in different pilots across Europe will be demonstrated through future activities of the DigiBUILD project. Within this context the project aims to develop various innovative applications, such as Electric Vehicles smart charging to increase renewable energy consumption, optimization of heat generation in 4th generation District Heating, and pro-active management and fault detection in buildings with a focus on enhancing occupant comfort.

Keywords—*Digital Twin, Energy, Smart Building, Smart Cities*

I. INTRODUCTION

To reach the European objective of reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 55% and reaching a share of 45% renewables in 2030, it is essential have an energy system (ES) which is ready to support the distributed generation (heat and electricity related) and the spreading of electric vehicles (EVs). According to International Energy Agency, in the next decades ESs need to be more connected, smart, efficient, reliable, and sustainable [1]. With these aims, European Union (EU) in October 2022 adopted an action plan [2] for promoting the investment in digital technologies such Internet of Things (IoT) devices, 5G connectivity, and Digital Twins (DTs) of ESs.

The term “Digital Twin” was coined by Grieves in 2003 [3] and gathered again in 2010 by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration [4] which defined a DT as a probabilistic, physics-based, scalable simulation of a system or vehicle which mirror the entire life of the real twin by the use of physical models combining real time and historical data. The DT discussed is ultra-realistic, includes high-fidelity physical models, historical sensors-data and real-time measurements. To maximize the success of the operation, a DT must also offer the possibility to be managed remotely and by itself.

A complete definition of DT was proposed in 2021 by Singh et al. [5]. According to the authors, a DT is a virtual model or simulation that closely mirrors a real-life object, process, or system, including its physical behaviours and characteristics, in real-time. The DT is kept up to date with current and historical data, allowing for a self-evolving and dynamic representation of the physical twin. The relationship between the DT and its physical counterpart is bidirectional, meaning that any changes made to the DT are also reflected in the physical twin and vice versa. Considering this definition, the DT is composed by the physical twin (i.e. the physical and real system considered which mutates during time), the Digital Model (DM) (which update and change itself by receiving real-time data from its physical counterpart and making simulation) and a linking mechanism (normally sensors, actuators and dashboards for user interaction).

In 2018, noticing an increase of the usage of the term DT in scientific literature, sometimes inappropriately, Kritzinger et al. [6] updated the definition of DT distinguishing it from a DM and a Digital Shadow (DS). The authors defined the DM as “a digital representation of an existing or planned physical object that does not use any form of automated data exchange between the physical object and the digital object”. In this case, the model can be both data-driven or physics-based but a real-time change in the physical object does not affect the DM and vice versa. If there is a one-way interaction from the physical system which update the digital object (i.e. a monitoring system), this meets the definition of DS. A DT includes a both-direction automated interaction between the physical system and the digital object.

Fig. 1. Digital Twin representation of a generic energy system

The results of their classification showed that only the 19% of the reviewed papers about DT applications in manufacturing met their DT definition.

This work aims to present latest academic literature about DT of ESs, analysing different applications, methods and final objectives, for finally presenting the DTs of the case studies in the framework of DigiBUILD European project. The novelty is related to the investigation of different publications for guiding future researchers suggesting different applications, reasons and the methods to develop a omni-comprehensive DT of an ES. This information will be strengthened also by the real applications in different pilots, with different objectives and models, in the project.

The remaining parts of this paper are organised as follows. In Section II the current State of Art of the DT technology in ESs will be presented. As mentioned before, different applications, methods and aims will be highlighted. The DTs which will be developed in DigiBUILD will be described in Section III. These include DTs of buildings, District Heating Networks (DHNs) and micro-grids for fault-detection and efficiency-increase purposes. Finally, conclusions will be presented in section IV.

II. CURRENT STATE OF ART

Although DT research for manufacturing purposes has reached advanced stages of development, its application in ESs is still in a nascent stage [7]. For this reason, this section concerns a comprehensive review of the current state-of-the-art of DTs-related research products in the energy sector. In first, different range of applications will be explored, including buildings, components, and smart energy networks.

Secondly the current section will focus on the modelling approaches followed by the authors in the development of their DTs. The possible aims of a DT will be also investigated for demonstrating the benefits and the need of this technology.

A. Applications

Within the context of the emergence of smart buildings through the integration of sensors, smart-meters, and IoT technologies, DTs are poised to become a prominent technology in the coming years. This is highlighted by a discernible trend in the literature, as demonstrated by the growing number of publications detailing the applications of DTs in buildings [8]. Aiming to improve the quality of teaching and the maintenance costs, a complete DT of an University campus is presented by Han et al. [9] The entire campus is modelled on Unity and it can be explored in the detail using the platform. The virtual model can be used also for different simulations (e.g. students can perform virtual hands-on exercises) or for monitoring purposes (i.e. vehicles

Fig. 2. Digital Twin Process [7]

traffic or sewage source in the river by detecting the content of pollutants). The paper presented by Hosamo et al. [10] succeeds in showing the advantages of having a DT of the building. The model they developed is capable of detecting in real time faults within the buildings (e.g. Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning systems, lights etc.) and can also forecast future faults for a better predictive maintenance. As mentioned before, DTs have been identified as a valuable tool for achieving net zero emissions targets in buildings while maintaining indoor comfort. In this framework an omni-comprehensive DT was developed in [11] to monitor, control, and forecast carbon dioxide emissions in a real residential unit. The infrastructure of this twin, including its IoT systems and model equations, is described in detail in the literature, providing a valuable resource for other researchers seeking to overcome the challenges associated with integrating Building Information Model, IoT, and Artificial Intelligence (AI).

Before modelling a complex network, DTs of thermal or electric power generation plants and DTs of single components need to be modelled for enhancing production efficiency while reducing operational costs and GHG emissions. The twin of a 200 MW Biomass Boiler modelled by Spinti et al. aims to achieve continuous efficiency optimization and, basing on collected data, the twin will update itself to keep it constantly current and cogent [12]. Geothermal power plant DM and an algorithm of optimization and forecasting using Machine Learning (ML) are studied by Buster et al. [13]. Their model was applied to several plants and forecasts have provided always accurate results. A DT for a heat pump is presented in [14]. The described model is capable of increasing its accuracy and computational efficiency through the use of a particle swarm optimization that incorporates real-time measured data. Furthermore, the proposed optimal control strategy, after forecasting of future building demand, demonstrated a reduction in energy consumption of up to 15% when compared to manual control method.

The spread of distributed energy resources (i.e. photovoltaic panels, micro-turbines, electrolyzers and thermal prosumers) and the diffusion of EVs, will lead DTs to be a key technology for their management. Cao et al. applied the DT technology in a micro-grid composed by different Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and Plug-In Hybrid Vehicles [15]. The simulations' results showed the best operation strategy for managing the available sources for minimizing costs also including algorithms for detecting cyber-attacks. Pan et al. developed a DM of a micro-grid made by an electrical storage, wind turbine, 5 Photovoltaic panels (PVs) and a building [15]. Using reinforcement learning they could plan a medium-term and long-term scheduling to optimize the yearly costs of electricity, the energy consumed by batteries and the energy from the wind generator. Since DHNs are affected by different types of faults, Bahlawan et al. provided a DT which can be used for fault detection in a real case study [16]. By using a novel diagnostic approach, results of simulation showed that single and multiple faults were detected and located, and their DT was able to calculate, with an error lower than 0,1%, the temperature and pressure of each node. Another DT application in DHN is studied by Lin et al. [17]. After an introduction of applications and outlooks of smart heating systems, the authors demonstrated the effectiveness of their model for calculating accurately the heat delay time and the pressure in each node of the district. With a smart management, tested in two-day pilot operation, they were able to reduce the use of Natural gas by up to 31% compared with conventional operation.

B. Materials and Methods

As described in the first section, a DT of an ES must include a dynamic model that accurately reflects the physical system's behaviour in real-time, and which can be simulated enhancing it with optimization and forecasting algorithms. The model must be capable of running in real-time, enabling changes in operational strategy and the detection of faults. This section will focus on methods for modelling, optimization-forecasting, and finally real-time operation that can be used to develop DTs of ESs.

Dynamic modelling can be approached by the use of physical equations which describe the system, data-driven algorithms or a combination of the two methods. Bondarenko et al. [18] proposed a DT model for a diesel engine, which is based on a physical analytical model that includes energy and mass conservation constraints, as well as the Wiebe combustion model. The authors discussed the challenges and existing methods for diesel engine modelling and presented their approach, which demonstrated promising results in accurately simulating the engine's behaviour. The previous cited DT of a biomass boiler [12] combine science-based model with data-driven algorithms (deep learning Bayesian analysis) to obtain the best results for simulations and reflecting the real system. In [19], the authors developed a data-driven method for modelling an industrial cooling tower. Analysing collected data and checking for linear correlations, different modelling approaches such as linear regression, simple regression tree, and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) multilayer perception were studied. The results showed that polynomial regression and linear regression were the best choices for estimating cooling capacity and electric power demand, in the case study considered. Iynkaran and colleagues conducted a study in which they developed ML models to predict power generation of a 7 MW solar farm DT in Australia [20]. The authors utilized data collected from the site to compare the performance of various forecasting models, including Support Vector Regression and Random Forest Tree (RF), and introduced two novel metrics for evaluation. Their results indicated that the ANN achieved the highest R2 value of 0.94. However, when considering the newly introduced metrics, the RF methods demonstrated superior performance.

A DT optimization control logic could be rule-based, as [21], but could also use some flexible models, for instance a mixed integer linear programming, genetic algorithm, or AI [22]. A DM was developed by Aklaghi et al. to optimize the operation of a dew point cooler using genetic optimization algorithms, feed-forward neural networks, and physics correlations showing a 72.75% improvement in COP and a 49.41% reduction in power consumption [23]. In order to accurately estimate the optimal solution, optimization algorithms require information about future variables such as solar radiation, wind speed, and building loads. AI-based forecasting methods are commonly used to provide this information. In a study conducted by Huang et al., 12 machine learning models were compared for their ability to forecast solar radiation [24]. Results showed that gradient boosting regression and parallel tree methods outperformed other models such as multiple linear regression, decision tree, and back propagation neural network. A DM for Milan Cathedral was developed by Angjeliu et al. with the aim of showing benefits of DT technology by optimizing monitoring and maintenance operations in historical masonry buildings [25]. The results

demonstrated that the simulation of dynamic measurements accurately reflected the structural behaviour of the real building and suggested the replacement of iron ties as part of the maintenance process.

In line with the definition of a DT, real-time simulation is essential to accurately represent the physical system and propose optimal solutions. Given these conditions, in the work presented by Hosamo et al. [10], basing on monitoring of occupants' comfort (thermal, visual and acoustic), different algorithms will be invoked for detecting the faulty system (e.g. Bayesian Networks, Air Handling Unit performance assessment rules, etc.). The visualization of monitoring data will be shown after receiving real-time sensors data using Revit and a plugin the authors developed. You et al. proposed a DT of a multi-vector ESs, basing on optimization algorithms and Deep Learning (DL) forecasting for enabling real-time intervention and predictive actions strategies [26]. Their model will self-update by learning for both forecasting errors and previous previsions and it has been evaluated considering different hypothetical case studies. Saad et al. investigated a methodology to create a DT for a smart grid with distributed generation combining IoT and power system components [27]. Their DT is mathematically formulated to represent the static and dynamic characteristics of the physical asset, it updates itself with data collected and enables the simulation of both normal and abnormal behaviours of a hypothetic asset. Ni et al. developed a cloud-based digitalization framework to collect and elaborate real-time data for a DT of a room in an historical building [28]. This data will be used for training ML algorithms to predict and optimize energy consumption and human comfort.

III. FUTURE APPLICATIONS IN DIGIBUILD

In the framework of DigiBUILD project, the partners aim to explore the potential of DTs to achieve different goals (e.g. energy efficiency, fault detection, costs reduction). This section will provide an overview of some of the different DTs that will be developed within this project. The majority of the pilots in this project focus on individual buildings or clusters of buildings, with Emotion and Heron featuring integration with EVs and RES. Meanwhile, Veolia comprises of two separate district heating networks, CP-Rio Vena and CP-Fasa which is a 4th generation DHN including Power-to-heat production.

A. UCL

The University College of London (UCL) is the leading multidisciplinary university in London and relies on a campus with more than 200 buildings of various uses. In the frame of the Project, two buildings, a residential facility and a teaching/research building, will be enhanced by the DT development. The DT will provide a simulation environment ("what if" interaction) to evaluate the impact operational parameter changes will have on sustainability and user wellbeing metrics. The DM developed will be able to calculate GHG emissions, Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) parameters and energy consumptions basing on different simulation inputs such as HVAC system schedule, set point or room occupancy.

Furthermore, the DT will display a 3D graphical representation of each building and provide forecasted, real-time and historical data of building energy consumption, temperatures and other relevant environmental parameters. The DT will also include data-driven fault detection algorithms for HVAC systems and sensors malfunctioning to support the building manager. By comparing consumption forecasting, thermal comfort parameters and real-time consumptions, the twin will identify possible critical issues and solutions to optimize the building operation. For this reason, a dashboard for showing reports and notifications of malfunctioning will be provided to the facility manager.

B. Veolia

VEOLIA, as Energy Service Company, is one of the global leaders in optimised resource management and aims to achieve a sustainable development of cities and industries; in this framework, two DTs will be developed for two thermal networks, named CP Fasa and CP Rio Vena, both located in Spain. The DTs mainly consist in a simulation environment addressing possible optimisation scenarios for both DHNs, aimed to increase the energy efficiency and reduce the energy costs for suppling the heat in the district. While CP-Rio Vena is a gas boiler-supplied network, CP-FASA is a 4th generation DHN that uses different sources of heat such as natural gas, biomass or excess electricity from PVs [29]. In both cases the twin uses models for predicting future

Fig. 3. Preview of the 3D view of Focchi's Digital Twin

demand and weather data to suggest optimal operation scenarios for controlling in real-time the boilers. The DT also updates its model with real time data to age as the actual network.

The twin will support facility manager in the improvement of operation and maintenance, through a dedicated dashboard for display the real system while showing real-time data, suggested strategies, and data quality report. All of this can be achieved through the detailed monitoring of more than 177 quantities such as fuel consumption, flow rates, pressures and temperatures at both boiler and dwellings level. To avoid the storage of wrong data that could negatively impact the training and updating of models, algorithms for cleaning and correcting raw data will also be included in the twin.

C. *Focchi*

Focchi is an Italian company specialized in architectural building envelopes. Within the context of the DigiBUILD project, a DT of the company's headquarters and the envelope factory will be developed. These two twins will be accessible through a web interface and will integrate data from various sensor providers and technologies. The buildings' layout and equipment will be modelled in 3D using an IFC model, which is a structured Building Information Model that describes the geometry, properties, and relationships of building elements. The DT will then be connected to a network of sensors installed throughout the building, including temperature, humidity, Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) concentration, and energy meters. This data are processed in real-time using advanced analytics techniques such as machine learning and predictive modelling, which provide a comprehensive view of the building's energy efficiency and comfort through detailed information on energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, and other key metrics. The system will be able to identify patterns and trends in the data, allowing for predictive maintenance and fine-tuning of the building's ESs. The twin will also perform anomaly detection, triggering alerts when it detects abnormal conditions such as equipment failures or temperature fluctuations. The expected benefits include improved energy efficiency, reduced carbon footprint, and increased employee comfort. By monitoring energy usage in real-time, the system will allow to identify areas where energy consumption can be reduced without sacrificing comfort or productivity.

D. *Emotion*

Emotion, an Italian company specialized in charging stations for EVs, has set its sights on developing a DT system to efficiently manage and optimize the energy consumptions of one of its buildings. The building is equipped with PVs with a capacity of 50 kWp and four charging points, each with a power output of 22 kW. The DT will provide, using optimization algorithms, the best strategies for charging the company's fleet of ten EVs, basing on the forecast of PV production, building consumptions and user needs. According to the FM command, the twin will interact autonomously in real-time with the charging point by starting and modulating the charge of a connected EV in order to reduce overall energy costs by using available PV power. Moreover, aiming to further minimize energy consumptions, the DT system will also act as a decision support system for managing electrical and thermal load by providing users with a list of manual actions that they can perform, such as modifying the HVAC set point temperature or switching the heat pump on or off. This algorithm will be launched in real-time to give the opportunity of save energy in case of surplus of electric power by PV.

This innovative system will display both historical and real-time data, including the energy consumptions, CO₂ emissions, and the costs avoided by using smart charging stations. The Emotion DT system will also ensure occupant comfort within the building, with feedback from occupants available through a dedicated web-app. The system aims to optimize energy consumption, reduce carbon footprint, and enhance occupant comfort, all of which are vital components in achieving sustainable and efficient building operations.

E. *Heron*

The DT created for Heron, a Greek power company, is designed to provide valuable insights into the energy consumption of a residential structure, including an apartment and an office. Once building, EVs' charging consumptions and national grid data are collected, the DT uses them to train a deep learning model for generating forecasts in a given future timeframe. Using this forecast the twin uses an optimization algorithm to match buildings load with energy produced through RES in the national grid by a smart EVs charging. This will be done using a decision support system which will suggest to the manager when will be the best moment to charge EVs in order to support the grid and reducing CO₂ emissions and costs.

The DT can also be used as a visualization tool for consumptions and emissions of buildings and EV charging stations using simple smart plugs and smart meters. By automatically generating reports for tracking energy consumptions, costs and emissions, this use case demonstrates the value of DT technology for enabling building managers to make informed decisions about energy usage and improve energy efficiency in residential structures.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A digital and sustainable transformation of ESs is a policy priority for the EU to achieve its energy goals. Efficiency in the use of energy and resources, decarbonization, electrification, and energy production decentralization necessitate a significant effort in digitalization. DTs will allow the creation of virtual replicas of physical systems that can be used for monitoring, design analysis, and optimization.

In this work, focusing on DTs of smart ESs, the literature has revealed a wide range of applications, including buildings, components, DHNs, and micro-grids. These applications have demonstrated the potential of this technology to improve the energy efficiency, sustainability, and operation of these systems. Despite that, some challenges remain, including the lack of a standardized definition of DT, the need for its application in real systems, and the associated difficulties.

Aiming to the future, DigiBUILD project presents a significant opportunity for the advancement of DTs by practical applications in 8 pilots such as buildings and energy districts. In this framework, the implementation of this technology will be

customized to address the specific needs of each pilot, with an emphasis on enhancing energy efficiency, detecting faults, and increase RES production taking advantage of a pro-active management of EVs and building loads.

In conclusion, this paper highlights the significant potential of DTs to transform the energy sector through practical examples and approaches. In the next future, it is crucial to further develop research in these technologies to achieve a more sustainable and resilient energy future.

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